

NANOTUBE REINFORCED POLYMER COMPOSITES: TAILORING THE INTERFACE FOR IMPROVED MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

Linda S. Schadler*, Kuiyang Jiang*, Rodney Andrews⁺, Ami Eitan*

* *Materials Science and Engineering, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute, Troy NY*

⁺ *Center of Applied Energy Research, University of Kentucky, Lexington, Kentucky*

ABSTRACT

Nanotubes are a very attractive reinforcing component for polymer composites due to their high strength and extremely high aspect ratio. The nanotube – polymer interfacial interactions are of major importance in enabling load transfer between the polymer and the nanotubes. We modified the surface of multi-walled carbon nanotubes by means of small molecules and polymer chains. The mechanical properties of nanotube reinforced polycarbonate composites were tested as a function of the type of the functional groups attached to the nanotubes. The optimal modification depends on the type of the bulk polymer matrix involved. In this paper we focus on the chemical modifications that were done and their effect on the ultimate mechanical properties of the nanotube reinforced polycarbonate composites. Our latest results on the optimal surface modification are introduced. The effect of the polymer nanotube interactions on the micromechanical behavior will be discussed.

Keywords: Carbon nanotubes, polycarbonate, composite, interface, mechanical properties

INTRODUCTION

The discovery of carbon nanotubes has introduced great opportunities in many scientific and technological fields. One important application of these materials is in reinforced polymer composites. Carbon nanotubes are unique in that their high modulus and strength [1,2,3] combined with their large surface area and aspect ratio could lead to combinations of mechanical properties not achievable with traditional fibers. Together with the opportunities that carbon nanotubes introduce, however, are some major challenges to be addressed. In order to utilize their surface area for interactions with the polymer matrix, carbon nanotubes have to be separated from bundles and homogeneously dispersed in the polymer matrix. Another challenge is the modification of the nanotubes surface, to enhance interaction with the polymer. Such modifications are more complicated in the case of carbon nanotubes, compared to carbon fibers, due to their almost defect free structure.

The most natural first attempts for preparation of nanotube reinforced polymer composites [4,5] demonstrated the potential in these materials, although the aspects of dispersion and compatibilization with the polymer matrix were not optimized. Multi-walled carbon nanotubes (MWNT) reinforced polystyrene composites were cast from a toluene solution. In these composites, the addition of 1%wt nanotubes caused an increase of 25% in the strength and 36% in the elastic modulus, compared to pure polystyrene[4].

The approach to separation and dispersion of carbon nanotubes in solvents has been the subject of several studies in the last few years. In order to form compatibility between nanotubes and solvents, most studies were focused on the covalent functionalization of the nanotubes [6,7,8,9] and on the non-covalent coating of polymers around nanotubes (called – wrapping) [10,11,12]. Formation of carboxylic acid groups on the nanotube surface was studied and analyzed for single walled carbon nanotubes[10] and MWNT[21]. The formation of these groups by acid treatment enables further reactions that can be more specific for compatibilization with a given polymer in a polymer composite material.

The present paper focuses on the mechanical properties of MWNT reinforced polycarbonate. The MWNT were used as received, and after chemical modification. In order to choose the route towards the best functional groups on the nanotubes, it is worthwhile to look at the work that has been done for the compatibilization of other chemical species with bisphenol A polycarbonate. One important example is the chemical reaction that occurs between epoxy based molecules and polycarbonate [13,14,15,16]. Scission of a polycarbonate chain in the carbonate group occurs at high temperature, by the hydroxyl group of an opened epoxide ring. Therefore, grafting of a lower molecular weight polycarbonate chain can be conducted by attaching an epoxidized molecule to the carbon nanotube and reacting these modified nanotubes with polycarbonate. This method is used here to improve the MWNT/polycarbonate interaction.

EXPERIMENTAL

Materials

MWNTs were produced by thermal chemical vapor deposition of a xylene-ferrocene feedstock at 700 °C in a quartz tube furnace [22]. The xylene-ferrocene mixture, continuously injected *via* a syringe pump, was volatilized in a preheat section and then swept into the reaction zone of the furnace by an Ar/10% H₂ carrier gas. The operating procedure was: the quartz tube and substrates were installed into the furnace and then purged with Ar gas; the furnace heaters were ramped up to achieve the desired stable temperatures; the liquid and gas feeds were started and run for a 2 hr reaction time. MWNTs formed on both the quartz tube wall and a flat quartz plate added for additional surface area, forming thick mats of well-aligned nanotubes that could be readily harvested by brushing the surfaces. Figure 1 is a FESEM showing the typical distribution in diameter.

Lexan 121 (General Electric) was chosen for the polymer matrix. Lexan 121 has a melt flow index of 17.5, tensile yield stress of 61MPa, and an elongation to break of 125%. Butyl glycidyl ether was purchased from Miller Stephenson (Heloxy modifier 61) and used without further modification

Figure 1: FESEM image of MWNT

Nanotube chemical modifications

The general scheme of the nanotube carboxylation performed in this work is:

The attachment of carboxylic acid to the surface of the nanotubes was done as follows. 100mg of CVD grown multiwalled carbon nanotubes were put into a flask with 400ml nitric acid (70%). The mixture was refluxed and stirred for 90 minutes. The mixture was then diluted with 600ml of water and filtered through a polycarbonate 10 μm filter. The MWNTs were separated from the filter and were put into 700 ml water and sonicated for 20 min. This was followed by another filtering step. The PH of the water was measured to assure that there was no residual free acid. The MWNTs were then dried at 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ under vacuum for 10 hours.

The extent of the carboxylation reaction was quantified using a titration method. Carboxylated MWNTs were added to de-ionized water and bath sonicated for 1 hr. A solution of 0.01N NaOH was added and stirred over-night. The dispersion was then filtered and washed with water. The filtrate was titrated with 0.01N HCl solution to determine the concentration of the NaOH in the filtrate. From the titration, the number of NaOH molecules that were attached to the carboxylated nanotubes could be assessed.

Further modifications of the carboxylated nanotubes included their reaction with butyl glycidyl ether (BGE) according to the following general scheme:

The procedure for this reaction was as follows. Dried, carboxylated MWNTs were dispersed in BGE by sonication. 1% of trihexyl amine was added as a catalyst, and the mixture was heated to 100 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ for 5 hours. The MWNTs were then filtered through a PTFE 0.2 μm filter, washed with

acetone, and filtered again. Qualitative and quantitative analysis of epoxidized carbon nanotubes is published elsewhere [19].

Preparation of nanotube/polycarbonate composites

The preparation of (as received or modified) MWNT reinforced polycarbonate composites was the following. MWNTs were dispersed in tetrahydrofurane by ultra-sonication in a water ice bath for 3 hours. Polycarbonate pellets were dried at 125 °C for 2 hours, followed by dissolution in tetrahydrofurane. The MWNT dispersion and the polycarbonate solution were then mixed together and ultra-sonicated for 1 more hour. The mixture was then dropped into stirred methanol causing precipitation of the composite material. The composite material was dried at 70 °C under vacuum for 3 hours and melted at 270 °C in order to avoid any residual crystallinity in the polymer. Dog bone shaped samples were prepared using a DACA injection molding machine. The barrel temperature was 290°C and the mold temperature was 140°C. The injection pressure was 125 psi. The dimensions of the samples were 25.0mmX4.0mmX1.5mm (length X width X thickness).

RESULTS

As received nanotube composites

The quality of the MWNT dispersion in the composite was examined by field emission scanning electron microscope (FESEM) of the fracture surface after the tensile tests. Figure 2 shows homogeneous dispersion of a 5wt% MWNT/polycarbonate composite. Figure 3 shows the stress-strain curves of the as received MWNT/polycarbonate composites for various MWNT concentrations. The elastic moduli of pure polycarbonate, 2%wt composite and 5%wt composite were 2.0GPa, 2.6GPa and 3.4GPa, respectively. The yield stresses were 60MPa, 67MPa and 71MPa respectively. These results show that load transfer is occurring between the polymer and the nanotubes even in the case of the unmodified MWNTs.

Figure 2: Fracture surface of 5wt% as received MWNT/polycarbonate composite

Figure 3: Tensile test curves of as received MWNT/polycarbonate composites and pure polycarbonate

Chemically Modified MWNTs

The first step in functionalizing the MWNTs is carboxylation. The carboxylated MWNTs were analyzed qualitatively and quantitatively in order to assess the concentration of carboxylic acid groups on the MWNT surface. A qualitative illustration of the presence of carboxylic acid groups can be seen in Figure 4. The dispersion in water of acid treated MWNTs nitric acid for different periods of time are shown. It is apparent that the longer carboxylation times resulted in a higher saturation point of the carboxylated MWNT dispersion in water, which is seen as a darker dispersion.

Quantitative analysis of the carboxylic acid concentration using titration confirmed the presence of carboxylic groups on the surface, and showed a concentration of 1.9×10^{-4} moles COOH per 1 gram of nanotubes, for the 90 minutes treated MWNTs.

The elastic modulus of the carboxylated and BGE modified MWNT/polycarbonate composites is presented in Figure 5, and is compared to the modulus for as received MWNT/polycarbonate composite. Note that the BGE modified MWNT/polycarbonate composites showed a significant improvement in the modulus compared to as received and the carboxylated

MWNT/polycarbonate composites. 5%wt BGE modified MWNT/polycarbonate composite had almost twice the modulus of the pure polycarbonate.

Figure 4: photograph of nanotube dispersions in water, after different reflux times in nitric acid

Figure 5: Elastic modulus of modified and un-modified nanotube composites

DISCUSSION

To develop MWNT/polymer composites with significantly improved mechanical properties, the MWNTs need to be well dispersed, have high aspect ratio, and have strong interaction with the polymer matrix. The dispersion is important for two reasons. First, agglomerates will act as defect sites and decrease the strain to failure. Second, the large surface area provides an opportunity to modify the matrix properties by potentially immobilizing the polymer chains [13].

The MWNTs that were used in this work were dispersed homogeneously in the polycarbonate matrix. The SEM image in Figure 2 confirms the separation and homogeneous dispersion. It is thought that the long sonication time during composite processing enables interactions between the as received MWNTs and polycarbonate chains to occur. Moreover, in the case of non-attractive surfaces, it has been shown [14] that low molecular weight polymer chains migrate to the surface. Therefore, the mechanism of reinforcement could involve an interphase layer of low molecular weight polycarbonate that is coating the nanotubes. This interphase will form the connection layer between the MWNTs and the bulk polymer matrix. This claim has to be further investigated in terms of molecular weights that are found in the vicinity of the nanotubes.

The high aspect ratio results in more of the MWNT length carrying load. This can be compromised during chemical modification (such as carboxylation) because it is thought that defects are introduced. During processing we have observed that defects can result in shortening of the MWNTs. We limited this by reducing the time for the carboxylation reaction such that the properties of the composite were not compromised compared to the as received MWNTs as is seen in Figure 5. Further optimization might be possible. On the other hand, there could be other reasons that there was no significant improvement in modulus for the 2 wt% as received vs 2 wt% carboxylated MWNT/polycarbonate composites such as: (i) the concentration of the carboxylic acid groups is so low along the nanotubes that the interfacial interactions between the nanotubes and the polymer chains remains the same as the case of as received nanotubes; (ii) the nature of the carboxylic acid groups is such that the chemical and physical attraction of the polycarbonate chains to the nanotubes is not changed. This finding was concluded recently by Raghavendran et al.[20] for the case of carboxylated carbon fiber polycarbonate composites.

Strong interaction is important both for load transfer and as a method for immobilizing polymer chains. The contribution of each is not well understood, but in other work we have found that the polycarbonate chains in the vicinity of the MWNTs are immobilized compared to the bulk polymer[13]. Thus, this likely contributes to the improvement in modulus of the composite. The appreciable improvement observed in the elastic modulus and in the yield stress, however, points to the BGE modification leading to better load transfer. The interaction between epoxidized nanotubes and polycarbonate is still to be confirmed, but it is known that cured epoxy systems can react with bisphenol A polycarbonate by trans-esterification reactions [15,16,17,18]. These reactions would enable the anchoring of polycarbonate chains covalently to the MWNTs through the epoxy based molecule. It should be mentioned that this reaction between the epoxy based molecule and the polycarbonate chains causes scission of the polycarbonate chain, and the attached lower molecular weight polycarbonate will be statistically distributed due to the random location of the scission along the polymer chain. This mechanism would, however, enable the formation of attractive interactions between the bulk polycarbonate and the nanotubes by, for

example, chain entanglement. These interactions can lead to improved mechanical properties of the composites based on BGE modified MWNTs.

SUMMARY

Multi-walled carbon nanotubes were dispersed in a bisphenol A polycarbonate matrix. The mechanical properties of as received nanotube reinforced polycarbonate were improved and showed a gradual increase with the nanotube concentration. Epoxide functional groups show promise as a direction for the compatibilization of MWNTs and polycarbonate. Micromechanical investigation of the interfaces in both types of nanotubes is ongoing.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the U.S. Army SBCCOM, Natick Soldier Center. The authors thank Prof. S. Sternstein, for his interesting insights. The authors also acknowledge Prof. C. Brinson and Dr. F. Fisher for their important inputs and discussions. Special thanks to Dr. Ben Ash for his assistance in every aspect of the work: from thoughts to conclusions.

REFERENCES

- [1] Salvetat J.P. et al., Phys. Rev. Lett., 82 (5), (1999), 944-947
- [2] Yu M.F. et al., Science, 287 (2000), 637-640
- [3] Yu M.F. et al., Phys. Rev. Lett., 84 (24) (2000), 5552-5555
- [4] Qian D. et al, Appl. Phys. Lett., 76 (20) (2000), 2868-2870
- [5] Schadler L. et al, Appl. Phys. Lett., 73 (26) (1998), 3842-3844
- [6] Liu J. et al., Science, 280 (1998) 1253-1256
- [7] Lin Y. et al., J. Phys. Chem. B., 106 (6) (2002), 1294-1298
- [8] Sun Y. et al., J. Am. Chem. Soc. 123 (22) (2001), 5348-5349
- [9] Bahr L.J. et al, J. Am. Chem. Soc., 123 (2001), 6536-6542
- [10] McCarthy B. et al., J. Phys. Chem. B., 106(9)(2002), 2210-2216
- [11] Czerw R. et al, Nano Letters, 1(8) (2001), 423-427
- [12] O'Connell M.J. et al., Chem. Phys. Lett., 342 (2001), 265-271
- [13] Fisher F., Eitan A., Schadler L., Brinson C., To be published (2003)
- [14] Van der Gucht J., Besseling N.A.M., Fleer G.J., Macromol., 35 (2002), 6732-6738
- [15] Zheng S., Guo Q., Mi Y., Chan C., J. Appl. Polym. Sci., 73 (1999), 1181-1190
- [16] Su C., Woo E.M., Chen C.Y., Wu R.R., Polymer, 38(9), (1997), 2047-2056
- [17] Li M.S., Ma C.C.M., Lin M.L., Chang F.C., Polymer, 38(19) (1997), 4903-4913
- [18] Li M.S., Ma C.C.M., Chen J.L., Lin M.L., Chang F.C., Macromol., 29(2) (1996), 499-506
- [19] Eitan A., Schadler L., Andrews R. Jiang K., in press (2003)
- [20] Vaghavendran V.K., Drzal L.T., Askeland P., J. Adh. Sci. Tech., 16(10), (2002), 1307-1326
- [21] Lin Y., Rao A.M., Sadanadan B., Kenik E.A., Sun Y-P., J. Phys. Chem. B., 106(6) (2002), 1294
- [22] Andrews R., Jacques D., Rao AM., Derbyshire F., Qian D., Fan X., Dickey EC., Chen J., Chem. Phys. Lett., 303 (1999), 467